

Oxidation of Hydroxyl Ion by Potassium Ferricyanide

SITANSU SEKHAR BHATTACHARYYA and ANSUMAN ROY*

Department of Chemical Technology, University College of Science & Technology,
92 Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Calcutta-700 009

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The oxidation of hydroxyl ion by potassium ferricyanide in solution has been studied. Under standard condition, the reaction is endoenergetic. Application of potential drives the reaction electrochemically rather than merely generate local concentration of hydroxyl ion at anode to produce both oxygen and ferrocyanide in the vicinity of the same electrode, as suggested earlier. With high hydroxyl ion concentration or ferricyanide/ferrocyanide ratio, the reaction proceeds spontaneously, and the second order rate constant is $2.2 \times 10^{-2} M^{-1} s^{-1}$ at 32° .

RECENTLY, the kinetics of oxidation of hydroxyl ion by potassium ferricyanide have been reported by Rao *et al.*¹. Some observations reported by the authors and their explanations prompted us to carry out the present work. These authors reported the following, (i) potassium ferricyanide solution is quite stable in alkaline medium, since (according to authors) the reaction is endothermic with an oxidation potential of 0.46 eV as derived from the equations,

(ii) That oxygen evolution occurs when a pellet of potassium hydroxide is added to solution of ferricyanide led them to suggest that a localised concentration of hydroxyl ion is needed for the evolution of oxygen and that localised concentration can be developed, according to the authors, even in dilute solution by applying a potential. Thus application of a potential between two electrodes dipped into the ferricyanide-alkali solution produces a localised concentration of OH^- at the anode, and this leads to the oxidation of OH^- by $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ with an evolution of oxygen. The reaction is not at all electrochemical, and both the oxidation of OH^- and reduction of ferricyanide are occurring in the vicinity of the anode. There is no conjugate reaction at the cathode.

The equation (1) of the authors,

is all right. The calculation of the endothermicity needs scrutiny. Equations (2) and (3) already referred to are incorrectly presented. The reaction (2) is a two electron process and the standard oxidation potential is -0.401 eV .

and the overall reaction is

The standard free energy change for reaction (4) is $23.060 \times 0.031 \text{ cal mol}^{-1}$, with $E^\circ = -0.031 \text{ V}$. The reaction, under standard condition is not spontaneous. The comment by the authors about endothermicity and non-spontaneity is alright although the magnitude is not correct. Schematically the electrochemical cell corresponding to the reaction is

and the E° is -0.031 V . The evolution of oxygen on addition of KOH bead in $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ solution may be visualised by consideration of change in the potential of the OH^-/O_2 half-cell with change in concentration of OH^- . High concentration of $[\text{OH}^-]$ say $10 \sim 20 \text{ M}$, with $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}/[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ ratio unity or each having unit activity will make the e.m.f. of the cell positive ($> +0.03 \text{ V}$), thus making the forward reaction feasible. Similar result will be obtained if one keeps the activity of OH^- unity and takes $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}/[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ as $10 \sim 20$. One could also just calculate the equilibrium constant of this reaction which is $K = 9.31 \times 10^{-2} \approx 0.1$ at 25° . This explains if one wants the reaction to proceed from left to right, $[\text{OH}^-]$ or $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ should be high. Application of a potential resulting in an increase in the local concentration of OH^- at anode, to drive the reaction and the process, is in no way electrochemical, as reported by them, does not seem to be logical. The observation that both the oxidation of OH^- and reduction of ferricyanide occur in the vicinity of anode and that there is no conjugate reaction at cathode with an applied potential of $0.4 \sim 0.9 \text{ V}$ between the electrodes (which means that there should not be any steady current flow between the two electrodes), is not likely as shown by the following study.

Experimental

All the solutions were prepared from AnalaR grade reagent using doubly distilled water.

A H-shaped glass vessel with sintered disc at the middle and with two platinum foil electrodes on two arms, gas collecting tube at anode and a saturated calomel as reference electrode, was used as the experimental cell. DC potential was applied from a regulated power supply and the potentials between the two electrodes as well as of each with respect to the reference were measured with a Philips PP-9004 DC micro-voltmeter. The current flowing through the cell was measured with a B.P.L. multimeter connected in series with the applied potential.

0.02 M $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$ and 0.02 M KOH solutions were mixed in equal volume and taken in the cell. pH of the cell solution was recorded in a Elico LI 120 pH meter. The spectra of the solutions were recorded on a Beckman DB recorder spectrophotometer. $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$ has λ_{max} at 415 nm ($\epsilon=1.05 \times 10^3 M^{-1} cm^{-1}$) and $K_4[Fe(CN)_6]$ at 350 nm ($\epsilon=9.5 \times 10^1 M^{-1} cm^{-1}$).

Results and Discussion

Before applying any potential between the two electrodes, their potential with respect to SCE were measured and both showed an equal value of +0.26 V vs SCE (i.e. the oxidation potential of the electrodes is $-(0.26+0.24)$ or -0.50 V vs NHE). pH of the solution was 12.15.

On applying a potential of 1.0 V oxygen evolution starts at the anode. A current of magnitude 2.0 mA flows initially, which gradually drops with time to 1.3 mA. The potential of the cathode shifts from +0.26 V vs SCE to -0.1 V (when current is 1.65 mA) and then to -0.22 V (when the current is 1.3 mA). After electrolysis for 8 min, when the current drops to 1.3 mA, stirring of the cathode increases the current to 1.9 mA and its potential becomes -0.03 V vs SCE. On passing current for 2.5 h (with an average current of 1.25 mA), 0.59 ml of oxygen is liberated at the anode. After disconnecting the applied potential, each electrode potential was measured with respect to SCE. While the anode potential remained unchanged at +0.26 V vs SCE, the cathode potential drops down to +0.16 V. pH of the solution in the anode compartment drops to 10.84 and that of cathode compartment is 11.40.

Fig. 1 shows the absorption spectra of the solution before and after electrolysis in the anode-half and cathode-half. This shows that the concentration of ferricyanide remains unchanged in the anode-half while it decreases in the cathode-half. The decrease in potential of the cathode after electrolysis, keeping the anode potential (vs SCE) constant, also indicates that ferricyanide reduction occurs at the cathode and not in the anode-half, suggesting that the reaction is purely electrochemical with OH^- oxidation at the anode and ferricyanide reduction at the cathode. Oxidation of OH^- to O_2 reduces the pH of the anode solution. Slight decrease in

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of 1.1×10^{-3} M ferricyanide in alkali (a) before electrolysis (---), and after electrolysis in anode-half (---), (b) in cathode-half (-.-); and (c) of 1.1×10^{-3} M ferrocyanide in alkali (-).

pH of the cathode solution also indicates that on electrolysis, OH^- ion acts as charge carrier and moves to the anode (mobility of OH^- is much higher than that of ferricyanide ion). From the magnitude of current the amount of oxygen produced at the anode and that of ferrocyanide at cathode have been calculated and these values are in good agreement with the values obtained experimentally. Under the condition, there was no evolution of hydrogen at the cathode.

TABLE 1

Average current	= 1.225 mA
Time of electrolysis	= 9060 s
Amount of oxygen to be liberated (calculated)	= 5.75×10^{-5} equiv. (2.875×10^{-5} mol)
Amount of ferricyanide reduced (calculated)	= 1.15×10^{-4} mol
Amount of oxygen produced (experimental)	= 2.6×10^{-5} mol (0.59 ml)
Amount of ferricyanide reduced (experimental)	= 1.02×10^{-4} mol

Fig. 2 shows the current—potential curve for 0.1 M ferricyanide and 0.1 M NaOH mixture, which shows sharp rise in current from 0.4 V, suggesting electrode reactions at those potentials, and the threshold potential for the reaction at above concentration is 0.4 V.

The above reaction was also studied at high hydroxyl ion concentration in absence of any applied potential. With 0.1 M ferricyanide no reaction has been observed to occur upto 5 M OH^- . At 8.5 M OH^- concentration, the reaction proceeds upto 33% at 32°. Fig. 3 shows the plot of $\log [Ferricyanide]$ vs time, indicating that the reaction is first order with respect to ferricyanide. The first order rate constant obtained from the slope of the line is

$1.9 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at $[\text{OH}^-] 8.5 \text{ M}$; thus the second order rate constant comes out to be $2.2 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

It has also been observed that addition of moderately concentrated alkali solution to solid potassium ferricyanide generated oxygen. The above results indicate that the reaction between ferricyanide and alkali under standard condition is endoenergetic and application of potential drives the process electrochemically thus liberating oxygen at anode and reducing ferricyanide to ferrocyanide at cathode. As suggested earlier that the applied potential results in an increase of the local hydroxyl

Fig. 2. Linear sweep voltammetry of 0.1 M ferricyanide in 0.1 M alkali at platinum electrode, scan rate = 100 mV s^{-1} .

Fig. 3. Kinetics of reduction of 0.1 M ferricyanide with 8.5 M alkali, plot of $\log(x_t - x_{\infty})$ vs time.

ion concentration at anode and this leads to the oxidation of OH^- by ferricyanide in the vicinity of anode without any conjugate reaction at cathode, is not correct.

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